

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component of Bioinformatics for LYN

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Literature research of LYN has been summarized extensively by P.M. Weerawarna et al. in “IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component Evaluation of Literature Compounds as Lyn Chemical Probes” <https://zenodo.org/record/8335611>. In this document, the evidence from BCB core research is summarized below.

LYN is a proto-oncogene and one of the tyrosine kinases in the Src tyrosine kinase family, which is involved in the regulation of mast cell degranulation, and erythroid differentiation. LYN is an indirect activator for PLCG2 through SYK. SYK is phosphorylated and activated by LYN then further activates PLCG2. LYN is dephosphorylated by PTPN6 and INPP5D, both of which are proposed AD microglia drug targets. Together with HCK, which is also a Src family member, LYN phosphorylates multiple proteins including immunoreceptor tyrosine-based inhibitory/activation motif (ITIM/ITAM) containing protein such as DAP12, which mediates the signals downstream from TREM2 receptor activation of microglia.

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Figure-1 LYN/HCK and PTPN6 in the microglia activation.

In a meta coexpression study, LYN was found coexpressed with other AD drug target candidate genes in the consensus module of microglia and immune module in DLPFC, STG, FP, IFG and TCX regions [1]. In our recent GWAS study with ROSMAP cohort, LYN, along with three other genes, was found to be marginally associated with increased AD risk (p value 0.0663).

In protein-protein interaction network (Figure-2), LYN is found to be closely interacting with PTPN6, since it is the direct target of PTPN6, and is dephosphorylated by the latter. It also interacts with VAV1, which is involved in macrophage, B cell and T cell development and activation, and also found to be an AD risk gene in the GWAS study of ROSMAP cohort (p value 0.0713).

Figure -2 The LYN PPI network from STRING database.

Although LYN is not observed differentially expressed in bulk tissue RNA-seq data when AD is compared to normal brain samples. In a 2018 study, LYN was observed to have lower enzymatic activity in the human AD brain samples, and was shown to play a crucial role in A β 1-42-mediated neurotoxicity and tau pathology by phosphorylating Fc γ receptor IIb2 [3].

Gene Symbol	Cell Type	Data Source	log2_foldchange	adj_p_value	Compare Status
LYN	excitatory neurons	[2]	-0.3841	9.36E-09	pathology vs no-pathology
LYN	excitatory neurons	[2]	-0.3552	1.80E-07	early-pathology vs no-pathology
LYN	oligodendrocyte	[2]	1.5271	1.21E-02	late-pathology vs early-pathology

In

single cell transcriptomic study [2], LYN was found to be down-regulated in MCI vs. normal and AD vs. Normal comparison in the excitatory neurons, while up-regulated in the oligodendrocytes (see table above).

In the ChIP-seq data analysis of H3K9 acetylation of ROSMAP cohort, LYN was found to be minorly deacetylated in the promoter region in AD vs. normal comparison (FDR 0.0014), which indicates a possibly minor decreased transcriptional activation of LYN, as well as a minor decreased acetylation between different APOE subtypes (ApoE4 vs. non-ApoE4, FDR 0.0002).

In our recent progressive study, LYN gene expression is found to be positively associated with disease progression in both male and female cohorts of ROSMAP.

Reference:

1. Wan Y., et al. Meta-Analysis of the Alzheimer's Disease Human Brain Transcriptome and Functional Dissection in Mouse Models. Cell Rep. 2020 Jul 14;32(2):107908. doi: 10.1016/j.celrep.2020.107908.
2. Mathys H. et al..Single-cell transcriptomic analysis of Alzheimer's disease. Nature, 2019 Jun;570(7761):332-337. doi: 10.1038/s41586-019-1195-2.
3. Gwon Y. et al. Amelioration of amyloid β -FcγRIIb neurotoxicity and tau pathologies by targeting LYN. The FASEB Journal, 12 December 2018 <https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.201800926R>